

Catholic Colleges and Social Transformation

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Abstract: Does education transform society as the topic of this session seems to suggest, or does society shape education? According to the author, this question has been answered at least in three different ways. The third perspective avoids the two extreme positions of social change through education or educational change through social revolution, and accepts a middle view, which may be termed the “relative autonomy thesis,” which the author finds most plausible. By providing some statistical data on Catholic higher education, the author suggests some areas of relevant action, like liberative thrust, promotion of justice, pedagogy of praxis and ethos of co-operation. The author concludes the article by affirming that in a world where so many pressures unconsciously condition the minds and the feet of our youth to the rhythmic drumbeat of the status quo, Catholic education should be able to offer students a different option – to become enlightened, creative non-conformists, committed to the cause of building the India of our dreams.

Keywords: Higher education, Catholic education, liberative thrust, promotion of justice, pedagogy of praxis, ethos of co-operation.

When one considers the topic of this session,¹ *Catholic Colleges and Social Transformation*, the question that poses itself right away is analogous to the proverbial “chicken or egg” puzzle. Does education transform society as the topic of this session seems to suggest, or does society shape education? This question has been answered at least in three different ways.

The first is the conventional view, which holds that the educational system can bring about key changes in the consciousness of a society, which in turn can transform its social, economic and political structures. It can promote social mobility, equalise opportunity and thus function

as an agency of individual and societal emancipation. This rather optimistic view of education is echoed in the policy documents put out by the educationists and planners. The Kothari Commission Report, for example, declared: "The destiny of India is now being shaped in her classrooms. This we believe is no mere matter of rhetoric... If societal change on a grand scale is to be achieved without violent revolution, there is one instrument and only one instrument that can be used: EDUCATION" (1.01; 1.14). Similarly, the Third Five Year Plan document stated: "Education is the most important single factor in achieving rapid economic development and technological progress and in creating a social order founded on the values of freedom, social justice and equal opportunity." Almost every policy statement on education has projected education as the single most important tool to reduce disparities, equalise opportunities and bring about orderly transformation in a peaceful manner.

In sharp contrast to this conventional view is the notion that educational institutions do not, indeed cannot, transform society. The scholars of this persuasion believe that envisaging the school or college as an agent of social change is an idea that is utopian in the extreme. Thus Paulo Freire, the renowned Brazilian educationist writes:

The schools where systematic education is developed do not shape society, but instead society shapes them. It is impossible to expect schools to transform society... The oppression of the masses, which is the problem of the exercise of power, was not caused by the schools and therefore will not be solved by the mere transformation of the schools. Transformation of reality cannot be mediated by educational changes. That would be a utopian panacea. On the contrary, it is the transformation of society by political action that will change education (1983, 21).

As a subsystem of society, the educational system is dependent upon and subordinated to the political and economic structures and the dominant value system of the society in question. Therefore, the educational system reflects and, in turn, reinforces the institutionalised inequalities in the social system.

The educational system is particularly susceptible to political manipulations. Those who wield political power will strive to ensure

that the educational system promotes and perpetuates their privileged position in society. They will oppose educational policies and initiatives that might weaken the existing power structure and result in a radical reconstruction of the society. As Freire puts it, "There is nothing like neutral education. Education is a political act. Those who wield power define what education is. They determine the ends it should pursue and what its methodologies should be... They cannot be expected to design the kind of education that will work against the preservation of their power" (1983, 21). Education, in this perspective, articulates the ideology of the dominant group in a society and socialises the young into the rituals of the dominant culture. The socio-economic and political emancipation of society must happen first, and then the transformation of the educational system will automatically follow.

The third perspective avoids the two extreme positions of social change through education or educational change through social revolution, and accepts a middle view, which may be termed the "relative autonomy thesis." I find this view of education the most plausible of the three. As Murickan has pointed out, "All education has a dual character. As a process of socialization it makes individuals conform to the norms and values of society and its establishment, thus dominating and domesticating them; at the same time it has the capacity to generate a spirit of inquiry and questioning of the accepted truths, thereby liberating the human mind from the shackles of the past and the present" (1995, 54).

Although education is subordinated to and largely conditioned by the socio-economic and political forces in society, it does possess a certain autonomy, which, if actualised, can lead to real, if limited, social changes. In other words, education is a dialectical process. Although it tends to legitimise and reproduce the status quo, it has also a liberative potential that can lead to social transformation.

Which of these two functions shall dominate and to what extent, depends largely on the educators and those who administer the educational institutions. Whether a college functions as an instrument of domestication or an agency of emancipation depends, in no small measure, on the choices we make as educators and administrators of educational institutions. As the Kothari Commission Report has long ago pointed out: "The naive belief that all education is necessarily good,

both for the individual or for society, and that it will necessarily lead to progress, can be as harmful as it is misplaced... It is only the right type of education, provided on an adequate scale, that can lead to national development; when these conditions are not satisfied, the opposite effect may be the result” (1.18).

I. Catholic Education and Social Transformation

Since the social functions of education are variable, whether education domesticates or liberates, whether it functions as a catalyst for social transformation or a bulwark of the status quo, cannot be deduced logically; it can only be ascertained empirically. In reality then what kind of a role do the Catholic schools and colleges play with respect social transformation in India today? Let us look at some pertinent empirical data.

Table 1 presents the views of the members of two major Religious Congregations of India – one, a Congregation of women, and the other, of men - on how effective their educational apostolate has been in terms of the goals articulated in their mission statement.

Table 1. Assessment of Educational Apostolate by the members of two leading Religious Congregations of India (% Responding “Agree”)

Our Educational Apostolate has been effective in:	(A) Women	(B) Men
1. Ensuring academic excellence	90	82
2. Providing educational opportunities to the Catholics	74	80
3. Inculcating discipline in students	68	76
4. Promoting human excellence/ integral development	52	55
5. Providing educational opportunities to the poor	51	26
6. Providing remedial education to weaker students	50	xx
7. Ensuring justice in education	49	48

8. Inculcating social consciousness and civic sense in students	37	33
9. Witnessing to Gospel values	28	24
10. Being agents of social transformation	21	23

There is a clear and consistent trend in the data. While the Catholic educational institutions are highly successful in promoting academic excellence, they are perceived to be least effective as agents of social transformation. Inculcation of discipline in students is a top priority in our schools and colleges. In contrast, development of social consciousness and civic sense in students receives low emphasis. Catholic educational institutions have done much in providing educational opportunities to the Catholics. But they have not been as successful in making education accessible to the poor or providing remedial education to the weaker students, who are by and large from the disadvantaged sections of society.

The data seem to suggest that the Catholic educational institutions as they function today contribute little to the social, political and economic emancipation of the country. And since there is no neutral education, any education that does not transform invariably serves to buttress the status quo, to perpetuate and deepen the existing system of institutionalized inequalities, power and privilege for the affluent few, and deprivation and exploitation for the marginalized many. It seems fair to conclude that Catholic education as it functions in India today seems to be more an instrument of domination and domestication than an agency of emancipation and transformation.

This is all the more paradoxical when one recalls the fact that the Church has always insisted that education, if it is to be authentically Christian, must transform not only individuals but also society. Catholic schools and colleges are an extension of the mission of the Church, which is to continue the mission of Jesus Christ. The mission of Jesus is perhaps best summed in his own words: "The Spirit of the Lord is upon me, because he has anointed me to preach the good news to the poor. He has sent me to proclaim liberty to the captives and recovery of sight to the blind, to set at liberty at liberty those who are oppressed, to proclaim the acceptable year of the Lord" (Lk. 4:16-19).

The mission of the Church to bring about a society based on justice, equity and freedom was repeatedly highlighted in the social teachings of the church over the past hundred years. This is perhaps best summed up in the dramatic declaration of the Third Synod of Bishops in 1971 that the work for justice and the transformation of the world is a “constitutive dimension of the preaching of the gospel.” Our schools and colleges, if they are to be true to their Christian character, must mediate the vision and mission of Jesus to bring good news to the poor, proclaim liberty to captives and recovery of sight to the blind and set at liberty those who are oppressed. This mission to participate in the struggle of the poor and the marginalized to bring about a just society is all the more significant in a country like India, where substantial sections of the population live in poverty, where centuries long discrimination based on caste had condemned the masses to a subhuman existence, where the barriers erected in the name of religion, language and other sectarian identities spawn hatred and violence.

More recently, this aspect of Christian education was highlighted by Pope John Paul II in his Apostolic Constitution on Catholic Universities, *Ex Corde Ecclesiae*. “The Christian spirit of service to others for the *promotion of social justice* is of particular importance for each Catholic University.... The Gospel, interpreted in the social teachings of the Church, is an urgent call to promote the development of those peoples who are striving to escape from hunger, misery, endemic diseases and ignorance; of those who are looking for a wider share in the benefits of civilization and a more active improvement of their human qualities; of those who are aiming purposefully at their complete fulfilment” (34).

II. Areas of Relevant Action

If higher education in this country is to serve the cause of a just society, profound changes in the educational system are imperative. There are several areas where the Catholic colleges can provide leadership to transform education and thereby transform society. I wish to highlight four such areas.

A. Liberative Thrust

“All education is either education for domestication or for freedom. That the non-elitist, transforming, prophetic, dialogical and critical pedagogy of Jesus is highly liberative is evident... This pedagogy was liberative in a double sense: it liberated people by making them conscious of their worth as children of the one Father in heaven... And as prophetic and critical teaching, it liberated them from the manipulative myths which legitimised their oppressive and alienating society by pointing towards a new fraternal and non-exploitative ‘world’ in which men and women could live together as brothers and sisters... Any pedagogy that claims to be Christian must be liberative in this double sense” (Soares-Prabhu 1985, 98).

A liberative pedagogy has necessarily a critical thrust. The present “banking system of education” is oriented to promoting in the students conformist and passive attitudes such as submission, acceptance of the existing order and fear of conflict. “In the banking concept of education, knowledge is a gift bestowed by those who consider themselves knowledgeable upon those whom they consider to know nothing. Projecting an absolute ignorance onto others, a characteristic of the ideology of oppression, negates education and knowledge as processes of inquiry” (Freire 1972: 46). Few teachers are aware of the contradiction between their educational ideal and the educational reality of which they are a part. On the one hand, the teacher in the role of absolute authority makes the students dependent, passive, uncritical and gullible. On the other hand, the students are constantly urged by their teachers to be bold, enterprising, creative and critical. However, the moment a student tries to live up to this ideal, he/she will be branded as a “deviant” or a “rebel”. The socio-logic of the educational practice rewards conformity and obedience and discourages initiative and critical outlook. This situation must change if our colleges are to become agents of liberative education. As Freire has pointed out: “Education must begin with the solution of the teacher-student contradiction, by reconciling the poles of the contradiction so that both are simultaneously teachers *and* students (1972: 46).

Teaching is made up of two components: content and method. Of these the content is usually considered to be the substance of the lesson. The teachers are there to “give” content, and the students are there to

“get” content. The task of the teachers is to “cover” content, and the duty of the student is to memorize and reproduce content. Method, on the other hand, is seen merely a means of transmitting content. The content exists prior to and independently of the method. The method is not important in itself; the method employed is irrelevant as long as the content is efficiently communicated.

This dichotomy between content and method in our educational system is what makes education a boring exercise in mechanical reproduction, rather than an exciting experience of critical and creative inquiry. Students are required to remember, not to inquire. If education is to become transformative, the medium must become the message. The critical aspect of any learning experience is the method or process through which learning occurs. How they learn is as important as what they learn. Students should not be treated as passive receptacles for the teacher to deposit the content. Rather the teachers should initiate the students into the process of critical search for answers to questions that are relevant to them. Students must play a role in determining what problems are worth studying and what procedures of enquiry need to be employed. Definitions must be formulated by the students, not dictated by the teacher. Students should be required to discover, not merely to remember. The “guess what I am thinking” type of questions, which the teachers normally ask in the class room, must be replaced with “tell me what you are thinking” type of questions. Whereas content-oriented teaching asks, for example, “who discovered America?”, process or method-oriented teaching asks “how do you discover who discovered America?” (Postman and Weingartner 1969). At its highest level, the purpose of teaching is not to teach – it is to inspire the desire for learning. Once the student’s mind is set on fire, it will find a way to provide its own fuel.

Furthermore, education to be liberative must cultivate in students “the art of mistrust” or “the virtue of doubt.” For just as there is no neutral education, there is no neutral knowledge either. All knowledge, as the sociology of knowledge emphasises, is socially constructed and socially maintained. Human ideation is a social process. The complex, blind mechanisms of society determine, often without our awareness – indeed, even against our intentions - the content of what is passed on as “objective knowledge.” In as much as all thinking is socially

determined, all knowledge is subject to ideological distortions or false consciousness. For every group, through a largely unconscious process, tends to create an understanding of reality that legitimizes its power and privileges. As Marx pointed out long ago, the ruling ideas of a time are necessarily the ideas of the ruling class. The interests of the dominant elite are often disguised and presented as objective knowledge and eternal verities. Liberative education must alert the students to the ideological biases that tend to creep into knowledge and empower them to debunk such distortions. A good teacher will not only make the students aware of the half-truths and beguiling fallacies produced and propagated by the dominant elite, s/he will go a step further and guard the students against his/her own, the teacher's, preconceptions and prejudices. This is perhaps the hardest task of a teacher.

B. Promotion of Justice

The All India Seminar on "Church in India" stated nearly four decades ago: "The Catholic educational endeavour should be part of the process of bringing about radical social change, specially by helping the poor and the underprivileged and by spreading the message of brotherhood and social justice through the entire network of relationships within the academic community...Unless the commitment to social justice and brotherhood of man becomes an active force in the actual working of Catholic educational institutions, they may not claim to be Christian.. The Church does not want its educational institutions to produce worshippers of success and security" (cited in Desrochers 1987, 219). Numerous documents of the Church have since reiterated this message: unless our educational institutions become genuine instruments to build up a just society, they are Christian only in name.

Education for a just society involves first and foremost ensuring justice in education itself. Justice in education calls for the equalisation of educational opportunity. This means providing equal access to education especially to those who have traditionally been denied access to quality education - the poor, women, the scheduled castes and scheduled tribes, and other educationally backward sections of the population. Equal opportunity in education involves not only equality in access to education, but also equal chance of success for all.

The principal beneficiaries of our system of higher education are boys, people of urban areas, and the middle and upper classes and castes. It clearly discriminates against women, the poor, the low castes, and the people of rural and tribal areas. A dualistic educational system has come to be established in this country, with a high quality elite sector and a low quality mass sector. There is segregation in education itself - the minority of private, fee charging, better colleges meeting the needs of the upper classes and the vast bulk of free, publicly maintained, but poor colleges being utilised by the rest. And this segregation has widened the gulf between the classes and the masses... (Kothari Commission 1, 36-37). Learning opportunities are severely skewed in favour of the rich and the powerful. Good education is available only to a privileged minority who can “buy” it.

Unfortunately, Catholic schools and colleges have also played a role in creating this segregation in education. Many, if not most, of the colleges run by the Catholic Church in India today are of the elitist type. In the survey of a leading Religious Congregation of Women cited above, as many as 56% of the members agreed that the schools and colleges run by their Congregation cater to the rich rather than the poor; only 26% disagreed. The same view was echoed by as many as 65% of the members of the Congregation of men mentioned earlier. In fact, more than two-thirds admitted that education has become more of a business than a ministry in their Congregation.

Recently the Church leadership in Kerala strongly resisted the measures introduced by the Kerala government to make professional education accessible also to the common man by streamlining admission policies and fee structure of the private self-financing professional colleges, many of which are owned by the Church. This is a sad commentary on the Church’s commitment to equal opportunity and social justice in education.

The elitist profile and academic excellence of Catholic private colleges make them very popular among the affluent sections of the society. Therefore, the rich and the powerful bring a lot pressure to bear on these institutions to secure admissions for their children. The affluent with superior individual merit and academic excellence find it easy to secure admissions in these colleges, while the students from backward castes and classes get pushed out of the system. The caste-

class exclusion in the educational system is often legitimized in the name of maintaining academic excellence. Time has come for elitist schools and colleges to make a choice between the prestige and power spawned by academic excellence and the service of the marginalised, which may entail some loss of prestige and power.

As indicated above, equalising access to education alone is not enough to ensure equal opportunity in education. Equalising access to our colleges is not all that difficult. Creating equal conditions for success for all in our colleges is a more challenging imperative. Equality demands that we adopt remedial measures to help the disadvantaged students to overcome the handicaps imposed by their background and culture. If we admit these students without the support of remedial teaching, we might be doing a disservice to them because underperformance would only exacerbate their sense of inadequacy. Secondly, the needs of the poor and the underprivileged students must be kept in mind in the recruitment of teachers, the choice of the curriculum, the selection of instructional aids, the preparation of tests and setting of the college time-table. Thirdly, the extracurricular activities of the college should be organised in such a manner that they contribute to the growth of all, rather than the development of some.

Even with remedial measures, academic results are likely to fall, at least to some extent. As T. Kunnunkal has pointed out: “Standards will fall .. and so will the school’s ability to win medals and certificates at state or national levels. But if we cater to those who can get an education even if we don’t provide it and thus neglect the many who have no such means, our Christian standards will fall. We have to make a choice between maintaining academic standards and Christian standards in our colleges. If a large number of students do well because of high capabilities and financial resources, are we not basking in borrowed sunshine? What glory is there in such achievement? Given the circumstances, our results are normal and to be expected. The real glory would be to make failures into successes, third into second, and second into first divisions” (as cited in Desrochers 1987: 285). Education for social transformation means that we have to educate the underprivileged in our schools and colleges even at the cost of lowering our academic standards to place them within their reach, and not beyond their capabilities.

C. A Pedagogy of *Praxis*

Praxis is a technical term that has its roots in Marxism. It refers to a method or model of thinking in general, and of learning in particular. One of Marx's breakthroughs was his discovery that rational or intellectual knowledge alone does not constitute genuine knowledge. We know best when knowledge is coupled with and challenged by action, when we are not merely objects of the historical process but its subjects. *Praxis* means unity of knowledge as content and knowledge as activity. It is acted upon reflection and reflected upon action, both rolled into one. This is perhaps best summed up in Marx's famous thesis on Feuerbach: "Philosophers have interpreted the world, the point, however, is to change it." If the students learn about, say, the gender bias in our society, but are not motivated to do anything to eradicate it, not only is such knowledge futile, it is dehumanizing as well.

Educational theories have in the past tended to emphasise the individual dimension of education almost exclusively. According to this view, education is primarily for the benefit of the individual. That is to say, the growth of the individual, the full and harmonious development of all his or her capabilities and talents is the principal, if not the sole, objective of education. Today this individualistic outlook has given way to a communitarian orientation. In this perspective education must benefit society at least as much as the individual. This has been underscored by the Vatican II Declaration on Education: "A true education aims at the formation of the human person with respect to his ultimate good and simultaneously with respect to the good of the societies of which he is a member..." (No. 1).

Education can perform this social role only if there is a close relationship between the college and the community of which it is a part. However, many, if not most, of our colleges now seem to live in splendid isolation from their surroundings, without any institutional commitment to the community and its concerns. This situation must change if colleges are to become effective agents of social transformation. Our colleges should find ways of being part of the community of the poor by getting involved in issues that concern them and rendering whatever assistance they can.

Such involvement in the neighbourhood is an important means of creating in the students a critical awareness of the social reality of India. It can help to open their eyes to the distortions in our society, the abject poverty of the masses, the gross inequality, the inhuman exploitation of the weak by the strong, the all pervasive corruption, the wanton destruction of the environment and so on. Creation of this awareness is crucial because we easily develop what Desrochers has termed 'the habit of unseeability'. This is a "psychological device by which we screen out of our field of vision disturbing factual evidence which would expose the falsity of our comfortable assumptions. To some extent, for all of us 'familiarity breeds disappearance'; we simply do not see the central facts of our social existence. Our students simply do not see the ugly reality of caste discrimination, the squalid horrors of slum existence, the malnutrition of masses of our people, the social dislocations of urban life, the chauvinistic divisiveness of language, caste, region and religion" (1987: 232). Our colleges should become effective agents of conscientization by relentlessly calling the attention of the students to the distressing facts of our social existence, shake them out of their apathy and motivate them to be committed to the creation of a just and humane society.

D. Ethos of Co-operation

The present education system is geared to promote competition rather than co-operation. The stress on self-development and individual excellence fosters individualism and self-centredness. "By favouring individual effort and success over teamwork, solidarity and co-operation, education inculcates individualism, selfishness, and even a certain mistrust of others. College situations often encourage brighter students to compete for a few places at the top, where winning comes only at the expense of losing. Moreover, our society rewards intelligence and high grades with scholarships, the guarantee of best jobs, salaries and perks. No wonder then that the bright people tend to look upon their talents as their own private property which they can use for their own self-aggrandisement" (Desrochers, 1987: 206).

It is often argued that healthy competition and rewarding the winners are necessary to bring out the best in students. But is competition, which projects a few as winners and the many as losers, ever healthy?

Surely, competition is neither the best nor the only way to bring out the best in the students.

This is not to suggest that teachers and educators condone laziness or be satisfied with mediocrity. They should motivate them to excel through service, compassion and co-operation rather than through competition, which breeds individualism and personal ambition. The brighter students can be urged to give of their best by helping the weaker students, thereby enabling the whole group to advance. Teachers can help the students to experience the joy and fulfilment that comes from offering one's talents and capabilities to enrich the lives of others, especially the weakest and marginalized in society. Team work and mutual help should be encouraged. Group marks could be given whenever possible. Instead of rewarding only personal achievements at prize distributions, altruism and social concern also should be recognised and rewarded. With imagination and creativity, the competitive ethos of our educational institutions can be replaced by a communitarian outlook. Students should be educated to look upon their companions not as rivals to be defeated, but as brothers and sisters to be cared for.

Conclusion

These are some of the different ways in which Catholic colleges can function as catalysts of social change. In his essay on "Self-reliance," Emerson wrote: "whoso would be a man [woman] must be a non-conformist." Apostle Paul tells us that whosoever would be a Christian ought to be a non-conformist. Indeed, this command not to conform comes ultimately from Jesus himself, the world's radical non-conformist, whose ethical non-conformity still disturbs the conscience of humankind. Catholic colleges cannot hope to be true to Jesus' legacy if the students they turn out easily allow themselves to be co-opted as the votaries of the existing system. To be authentic, Catholic colleges must offer an education with a difference, for a difference. In a world where so many pressures unconsciously condition the minds and the feet of our youth to the rhythmic drumbeat of the status quo, Catholic education should be able to offer their students a different option – to become enlightened, creative non-conformists, committed to the cause of building the India of our dreams.

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- 1 This is a revised version of a paper presented at the National Conference on Church and Higher Education in India organized by Stella Maris College (Autonomous), Chennai, 23-24 February 2007.